

TRADITIONS OF STUDYING THE PROBLEMS OF COMPETENCE IN THE
PEDAGOGY OF UZBEKISTAN

<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.6517704>

Luiza Jumatova Tozaboy qizi
*student of the master's department of
Tashkent State Pedagogical University
named after Nizami*

Annotation: *This article describes the content and essence of the tradition of studying the problems of competence in the pedagogical science of Uzbekistan.*

Keywords: *Competence, competence, cognitive, internal motivation, object, educational standards, levels, active position.*

Introduction. At present, the search for ways to increase the effectiveness of vocational education are associated with a competency-based approach. The relevance of the competency-based approach is emphasized in the materials on education modernization and is considered one of the important rules for updating the content of education. This is because a professional activity is characterized by increasing complexity and dynamics, the main task of competency-based training is to form a specialist who can solve professional problems in new situations. In the scientific and pedagogical literature, there are synonymous concepts of "competence" and "competence". Let us now turn to J. Raven's "Competence in Modern Society," where the author provides a detailed interpretation of competence.

This phenomenon, according to the scientist, "consists of a large number of components, many of which are relatively independent of each other. Some components are more cognitive, while others are more emotional. These components can replace each other as components of effective behavior. The term "competence components" means "those qualities and abilities that enable people to achieve important goals personally" and emphasizes that "competence includes only abilities". This also implies that internal motivation is not included in the concept of ability. There are also attempts in the scientific literature to differentiate the application of these concepts: Competence is a trait given to

an individual as a result of evaluating the effectiveness of a particular set of tasks, efforts to solve problems. It is important for a particular society.

Materials and methods. Competence is a parameter of the social role, which manifests itself in the personal sense as ability, that is, the suitability of the individual. Competence, according to G.Selevko, is understood as "an integral quality of an individual, manifested in the general ability and readiness for their activities, based on knowledge and experience gained in the process of education and socialization, and aimed at independent and successful participation activities".

Thus, analyzing the views of scientists on the essence of the concepts of "competence" and "competency", we can draw the following conclusions:

In the scientific and pedagogical literature, the term "competence" is used in two senses: knowledge acquired in the learning process, experience, general ability to act in a particular situation based on values, and a specific standard, of education. As a result, or in other words, a requirement for a specialist who intends to occupy a job position and perform professional functions based on active, responsible action;

The concept of "competence" is much broader than knowledge, skill, because it refers to the ability to apply generalized knowledge and skills to solve specific situations and problems that arise in real activity, and it refers only to knowledge (cognitive) and activity (behavior. attorney) but also relational components;

In the scientific literature, along with the concept of "competence", there is the concept of "competence", which in some cases is used as a synonym; Scientists are trying to differentiate these concepts, but there is no single position here either.

Results. Khutorsky competence is a set of interrelated personality traits (knowledge, skills, abilities, methods of activity) that is established about a certain range of objects and processes and are necessary for effective action against them, and competence is the possession, the appropriate authority of an individual, including his or her attitude towards him or her and the subject of the activity. Over the past decade, forums, conferences, scientific and pedagogical publications, and journals have been actively discussing the design of competency-based training technologies for future professionals, improving the educational process at the university based on a competency-based approach. Many dissertations have been devoted to these issues, including S.Sh. Palferova, "Designing Competency-Based Teaching Technology for Natural Science Cycle Sciences for Technical

University Students (on the Example of Mathematics)" (2003), T.I. Biryukova "Formation of personal competencies of medical students in the process of learning a foreign language" (2008), T.G. Vaganova "Teaching physics on a modular-competence the basis for junior students of technical universities" (2007) and others.

Federal Education Standards for New Generation Higher Vocational Education is a set of requirements required by state-accredited Russian universities to implement undergraduate basic education programs (BEPs). The requirements for the results of mastering the basic educational programs for the bachelor show the skills, not the knowledge and skills that the graduate should acquire.

Discussion. Thus, the transition of the pedagogical idea to the task of forming the competencies of the future specialist, in particular, the teacher of fine arts is normally strengthened and announced in the standards of the new generation. In this regard, it is becoming increasingly important to study the didactic possibilities of competency-oriented training of students – future teachers of fine arts and to put these ideas into practice.

Identifying the main ways for the successful organization based on competence For pedagogical-oriented education is first necessary to identify and disclose the principles of such work. The problem of pedagogical laws, principles, and rules is studied in the works of Yu.K. Babanskiy, V.I. Zagvyazinskiy, I.Ya. Lerner, V.V. Kraevsky, et al. In pedagogy, "Principles are the basic starting point of any theory, the guiding ideas, the basic rules of behavior". Zagvyazinsky is an expression of the

pedagogical concept, expressed in the form of knowledge about the essence, content, structure, knowledge of its laws and regulations, norms of activity, and regulations for practice, given in the categories of activities. Thus, the principles reflect the basic requirements of the organization of any activity, indicate its direction, and help a creative approach to building a particular process.

The level of development of students' professional competencies, in our opinion, can be described as follows:

High level: the student has a system of professional knowledge considers the proposed questions from different positions, confirms the theoretical rules with his examples; based on the conditions of a particular pedagogical situation, able to update and find the right professional knowledge;

Intermediate level: the student describes the theoretical positions on these issues with reasonable, complete, practical examples; offers a unique solution to a pedagogical problem;

Low level: the student defines the basic theoretical rules on the proposed questions; demonstrates the ability to solve pedagogical problems.

The meaning of competency-oriented education lies in the dialectical synthesis of academic and pragmatic education, enriching the subject's personal experience in constructing such education. The learning environment helps to optimally develop the individuality and uniqueness of the student, taking into account these universal values. The thesis that "there are no people who can't be replaced" is a thing of the past. Society enriches and develops due to the uniqueness of the representatives of culture. Following the strategy of modernization of the Russian general secondary education system, the teacher is called upon to ensure the integration and continuity of the processes of formation of universal knowledge, skills, and the formation of core competencies.

Important components of a teacher's preparation for student-centered learning are:

- The teacher understands the objective need for change in the education system and takes an active position on the issue under consideration;
- Understand the meaning of the terms "competency", "competence" and "competency-oriented education";
- ability to solve open problems (ie, without a clearly defined condition, without a predetermined solution algorithm, multi-answer problems);
- have methods and algorithms for designing a modern learning process to optimize its elements.

Conclusion. Our children are the representatives of a new generation, a new information society. Gradually, we see basic educational competencies becoming a means of development. Education is rising to a new level. Close cooperation and interaction of all subjects of the pedagogical process based on the implementation of a competency-based approach provide adequate conditions for the development, education, and upbringing of the child by his needs and abilities. It helps the student to quickly adapt to the world around him, cope with difficult life situations, rise to a high level of moral and personal development, to become a more the qualified and competitive subject of society, a full citizen of our country.

REFERENCES:

1. Bermus A.G. "Problems and prospects of introducing a competency-based approach in education." // Electronic resource: EIDOS online journal.
2. Zimnyaya I.A. Human competence is a new quality of education. // Problems of quality of education, M: 2003.
3. Lebedev O.E. "Competence The approach in Education." // school technology. 2004.- №5.
4. Rachevsky E. L. "Competence-oriented school: ways of being" - Perm: 2008.